

FACTOR AFFECTING CAREER PROMOTION OF EMPLOYEES IN BANKING SECTOR OF NEPAL

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Abstract

Introduction: Banking career are lime light opportunities in Nepalese commercial sector. Banking sector being the economic backbone of Nepal where banking employees are pillar of these standing foundation. Hence, banking employee's needs has to address timely and properly. Among various necessity of banking job, career promotion is one essential factor. However, the enlarge volume of turnover rate of employee retention reveals the subdue lacking in employee skill development related necessity. This under prevailed focus on banking employee's career development has increased banking turnover ratio which ultimately decline the banking performance. Thus, to reduce the impact of affect on career promotion of employees in banking sector of Nepal in-depth study is needed. Glimpse of spark of career promotion can help to retain employee for longer tenure in corporate sector which helps in maximizing the profitability of banking sector.

Objectives: In the banking sector, preceding problem regarding performance enhancement of bank has been the to and fro movement of employee in banking sector. To overcome such problem employee has to be motivated and promoted timely. Thus, the main aim of research is to explain the factor affecting the career promotion of employees in banking sectors of Nepal.

Design: This research is related with the subject matter regarding the factor influencing the career promotion of banking employees in Nepalese banking sector. The core subject matter of research is the primal topic of discussion in the aftermath of global pandemic. Hence, the research adopts the quantitative research design for analysis. To find the ground reality, researcher use wide spectrums of self designed questionnaire techniques. The research also measured the data through various statistical tools which prefect the justified fact from the angle of employee's spectrums. Quantitative research design used in this research also analyzed the adopted answers through static charts and graphs.

Findings: To enhance the economic progression in developing countries, banks have to play the crucial role. Banking sector being the limelight sector for new comer's job seeker has to maintain their glory through proper employee development practices. Thus, need of skill development and career promotion become inheritant in banking sector. This research thus revels the significant relationship between employee career growths with banking performance enhancement. This research identify various factors which helps in career promotion of banking employee which ultimately can be movers for strengthen banking success. Among various factors banking sector highlight the core factor which can enhance the career promotion of employees in banking sector of Nepal.

Practical Implication: Researcher has higher potential to define the means for enhancing the employee efficiency of banking sector through identification of various core factor of career growth. The research touches the wider angle for rigorously understanding employee need of banking sector of Nepal. This research is also the essence of banking growth in current aftermath of pandemic situation. Likewise, research helps to draw attention of policy maker for understanding the necessity of employee in current corporate world.

Originality/ Value: This research paper is based on primary research work carried out through ground based research where data are collected from self structured questionnaire. Since, researcher is done from field survey of banking sector research is original and higher reliability.

Keywords: Career, Performance, Banking sector.

1. Introduction

Banking sector are the foundation of Nepalese economy. They support and help economic progression through the flow of liquid assets in developing market like Nepal. In the mean time, when tech savvy world, present challenges every now and then banks define the ways to overlook such problems. Hence, banks are garland of corporate sector. However, in Nepalese corporate sectors, banks are under prevailed with many criterion and directives that banks often focus on management of external factors (Chauhan, 2019). As result, focus on internal aspects lacks extremely. Thus, employees working in banks are generally given marginal support from banking look out. This ignorance has led banking sector in problems of rapid employee turnover. There are various reason of employee turnover among them primary causes of employee leaving the banking organization is due to lack of career promotion. Banking employee has to undergo with many challenges to achieve banking objectives (Chalise, 2019). But, those hard work put on by banking employee are not timely rewarded in terms of career growth in banking sector which results on higher ratio of employee turnover.

1.1.Objective of the Study

The objective of the study on the title “**Factors affecting career promotion of employees in banking sector of Nepal**” are as follows:

- To analyze the factors affecting career promotion in banking sector of Nepal.
- To identify the higher level job title and salary range in banking sector of Nepal.
- To explore the job responsibilities in banking sector of Nepal.
- To assess the authority in banking sector of Nepal.

1.2.Hypothesis of the Study

The hypothesis of the study on the title “**Factors affecting career promotion of employees in banking sector of Nepal**” are as follows:

H1: There is positive relationship between career promotion and higher level job title.

H2: There is positive relationship between career promotion and salary range.

H3: There is positive relationship between career promotion and job responsibilities.

H4: There is positive relationship between career promotion and authority.

1.3. Problem Identification

Hectic work schedule are quite common in banking sector. Banking employee often has to face array of huddles in balancing work life. Banks being the leader of economic entity of developing countries has to put on their maximum effort to get desired outcome of national development. Therefore, banking employee has to put their utmost efforts to achieve institutional objectives. This creates challenges for human resource department of bank as banks has to motivate employee to perform better. There are various factors to motive employees to work hard and promotion can be the best tools for enhancing efficiency of banker (Falahat, Gee, & Liew, 2019). However, promotion can backfire if under efficient employee are promoted. Thus, banking institution has to understand factors affecting career promotion for enhancing performance of banking employees.

1.4.Rationale of the Study

In the mean time, banking employees are the hardest working personnel of corporate sector. As banking sectors are full of challenges and competitiveness, employee has to put best performance. Therefore, banking employees need motivation and timely appraisal from management sector for keeping up performance. In this regards, career promotion can be the tools for motivating employee. Role of bank is crucial for leading economy and employees are inevitable factor in success of bank. Therefore, this research helps to understand the factor affecting career promotion of employees in banking sector.

1.5.Scope of the Study

Research has extended scope and cover array of sectors. This research is indulging for banking sector as it provides the definitive solutions for countering employee turnover in banking sector. Banks are tech savvy sector whose consistence depends upon the employee. Thus, this research is crucial for enhancing banking performance and is effective for making policies in financial institutions. Research also provides the inside about the need of employee which helps to draft the efficient policies for employee welfare. As research is directed towards the banking sector, research provides the unidentified factors for motivating employee through career promotion in banking sector.

2. Social Cognitive Theory for career promotion

This theory is the new paradigm in the field of career development. It state career development from different aspects. The social cognitive career theory relates the importance of career development in banking sector (Wendling & Sagas, 2020). The various interrelated aspect of career development as addressed by social cognitive career theory such as academic and interest development for career development, career choices and career success (Lamorte, 2019). The social cognitive theory explains how career related needs can explain the employee job satisfaction. This can be shown from following figures:

Source: Brown, Steven D.; Lent, Robert W. (2011)

This theory shows the assessment of career development through ability. It also explains how ability is associated with self efficacy and outcome expectation. These conversion of ability into performance process helps in success of banking institution.

3. Literature Review

The literature review is the extended learning which broader the knowledge of subject matter. The previous scholar research also guides the path for leading research ahead. In contemporary context, understanding can leads to innovation thus literature review helps to promote learning. Literature review therefore is the prior learning of analyzing the subject matter of study. In this research to understand the subject matter, researcher has segregate learning in dependent and independent variables thoroughly.

3.1. Dependent Variable

Dependent variable is the variable which controls the subsequent changes that occurs in independent variables. The dependent variable is examined by analysis generally through numeric justification in quantitative research. Dependent variables are very significant to show relationship between variables. The dependent variable is tested in survey under array of circumstances to know the effect on relations (Helmenstine, 2020).

3.1.1. Career Promotion

Commercial banks are the organization which renders service to their customer continuously (Chauhan, 2019). Therefore, employees of commercial bank have to work with high morale as their work schedules are hectic (Pathak, 2016). It is very difficult to identify the needs of employee but career promotion can definitely be the boosting factor for enhancing promotion of employee. Career promotions are associated with various factors such as job title, responsibility, range of compensation and authority. Career promotion thus, help employee to perform better in organization and is influencing factor for job satisfaction (Neupane, 2019).

3.2. Independent Variable

Independent variables are the effect whose manipulation can helps to draw result in research. They are the variable which helps to test dependent variables. In this research, higher level job title, salary range, job responsibilities and authority are the independent variables.

3.2.1. Higher level Job Title

Higher level job title can helps employee to fulfill self actualization needs (Lekic, Vapa-Tankosic, Mandic, Lekic, & Mijailovic, 2020). Higher job title also provides the leadership role and supremacy to do work. This made employee more independent and innovative on executing ideas which are essence of banking job (Dikshit & Jain, 2017). Higher level job title provides autonomy to employee which helps in enrichment of performance. The job supremacy always leads to enhance organizational performance too (Gautam, 2016).

3.2.2. Salary Range

The employee work hard for getting the handsome pay. As in banking sector, longer working hours are quite common therefore salary range has to match the hardship they put on to their jobs. There is nothing like proper pay scale but management has to decide the ranges of payment according to efficiency and need of employee (Chiekezie, Emejulu, & Nwanneka, 2017). Salary range can definitely be the factors for mitigating employee retention in Nepalese commercial banks (Chalise, 2019).

3.2.3. Job Responsibilities

The employees who are hard working always seek for the challenges. Employees of banks thus have to be provided with job responsibility in competitive job environment. The job responsibility also helps to engage employee towards the job which ensure the reduction on employee turnover (Rahman, 2017). Job responsibility also helps to enhance productivity (Nusratova & Khadjieve, 2020). Responsibility also make employee responsible towards their duties for performing better every time.

3.2.4. Authority

The employee has to work in different challenges and scenario in banking sector. Management in banking institution has to implement the proper managerial style for motivating employee (A., Essien, Olusegun, Mukaila, & Adesina, 2013). The positive vibes created by management helps in enhancement of employee's performance (Falahat, Gee, & Liew, 2019). Authority therefore, counts as the valued factor for employee engagement in banking institution. Authority also helps to satisfy the employee esteem needs which can enhance the job satisfaction of employee.

3.3. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Conceptual framework is the research design which is prepared beforehand to conduct the research in systematic ways. It also shows the way to find the answer of research queries through the analysis of variables. It is the path which helps researcher to go on through the core of subject matter. In this research, research has taken two variables for addressing the answers of research queries. It can be shown as follows:

Figure 3.3. Conceptual Framework of the Study

4. Research Methodology

4.1. Instrument of the Study

The instruments of the study is SPSS software which analyses the data using the Likert scale questionnaire. The variables in the study is developed through the past studies. Different literatures related to the career promotion, higher level job title, salary range, job responsibilities and authority are studied for developing the questionnaire. All together 25 factors are developed for the research work.

4.2. Data Collection

The data is collected on the basis of the dependent variable i.e. career promotion and the independent variable i.e. higher level job title, salary range, job responsibilities and authority. The simple random sampling method is used to analyze the data. Primary data are collected from the respondents in the bank whereas, the secondary data are collected through the different literatures.

4.3. Research Design

Quantitative research design is used to analyze the data. The survey in the study meets the objective of the research and solve the research problem of the study. The quantitative research design in the study determines the relationship between the variables. All the observed data are calculated through the mathematical calculation using SPSS software. The data are calculated using the numeric form. The analysis provided in the research insights the future researcher to make the better decision.

4.4. Population for the Study

The population in the study is the commercial bank in Nepal. All 27 'A' graded commercial bank is used in the study. The top level management, officer level and the assistant level are respondents in the recent studies. 135 respondents are selected randomly for the study.

5. Data Analysis and Findings

5.1. Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis shows the correlation matrix between the variables. The Pearson correlation explains whether the variables has the positive or negative correlation between each other. In this study the positive or negative correlation between the career promotion and higher level job title, career promotion and salary range, career promotion and the job responsibilities and career promotion and authority are studied in the present study.

Table 5.1. Correlation Analysis

		Career Promotion	Higher Level Job Title	Salary Range	Job Responsibilities	Authority
Career Promotion	Pearson Correlation	1	.814**	.748**	.610**	.574**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0	0	0	0
	N	135	135	135	135	135
Higher Level Job Title	Pearson Correlation	.814**	1	.814**	.705**	.638**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0		0	0	0
	N	135	135	135	135	135
Salary Range	Pearson Correlation	.748**	.814**	1	.721**	.622**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0		0	0
	N	135	135	135	135	135
Job Responsibilities	Pearson Correlation	.610**	.705**	.721**	1	.642**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0		0
	N	135	135	135	135	135
Authority	Pearson Correlation	.574**	.638**	.622**	.642**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0	
	N	135	135	135	135	135

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

H1: There is positive correlation between Career Promotion and Higher Level Job title

The analysis of career promotion and higher level job title is tested through correlation analysis. There is positive correlation between career promotion and higher level job title. The correlation coefficient between career promotion and the higher level job title is .814. The p-value observed in the analysis is less than 0.01. Thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted.

H2: There is positive correlation between Career Promotion and Salary Range

The analysis of career promotion and salary range is tested through correlation analysis. There is positive correlation between career promotion and salary range. The correlation coefficient between career promotion and the salary range is .748. The p-value observed in the analysis is less than 0.01. Thus, hypothesis 2 is accepted.

H3: There is positive correlation between Career Promotion and Job Responsibilities

The analysis of career promotion and job responsibilities is tested through correlation analysis. There is positive correlation between career promotion and job responsibilities. The correlation coefficient between career promotion and the job responsibilities is .610. The p-value observed in the analysis is less than 0.01. Thus, hypothesis 3 is accepted.

H4: There is positive correlation between Career Promotion and Authority

The analysis of career promotion and authority is tested through correlation analysis. There is positive correlation between career promotion and authority. The correlation coefficient between career promotion and the authority is .574. The p-value observed in the analysis is less than 0.01. Thus, hypothesis 4 is accepted.

6. Conclusion

The factors affecting career promotion of employees in banking sector of Nepal is observed through the correlation analysis in the study. The variable in the study are career promotion, higher level job title, salary range, job responsibility and authority. Correlation analysis is used to analyze the data. The analysis shows the positive correlation between all dependent and the independent variable. Thus, from the survey in commercial bank in Nepal shows that there is better career promotion in banking sector in Nepal. Future researcher can use other variables and the other research design except the researcher has used in the study.

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